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FAIR2Adapt

FAIR2Adapt
Deliverable 5.2 – User Requirements Report

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Deliverable 5.2 - User Requirements for FAIR and scientifically sound CCA [M3-M18]

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	studies, forming the basis for defining targeted action plans leading to reusable FAIR digital objects in Climate Change Adaptation.
Keyword List:	user requirements, case study, FAIR Implementation Profile, Semantic Interoperability Profile, metadata schema, metadata vocabularies

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	11
2. Methodology.....	12
2.1. User story driven requirements.....	12
2.2. FAIR analysis using FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP).....	13
2.3. Stepwise requirement elicitation process.....	17
3. Case study specific requirements.....	23
3.1. Case Study 1 - Spread of radioactive isotopes in the Arctic.....	24
3.1.1. Case Study Description.....	24
3.1.2. User Stories.....	25
3.1.3. FAIR Implementation Profile.....	28
3.1.4. Gap Analysis.....	30
3.2. Case Study 2 - RiOMar Project.....	31
3.2.1. Description.....	31
3.2.2. User Stories.....	32
3.2.3. FAIR Implementation Profile.....	35
3.2.4. Gap Analysis.....	36
3.3. Case Study 3 - Hamburg City.....	37
3.3.1. Description.....	37
3.3.2. User Stories.....	37
3.3.3. FAIR Implementation Profile.....	40
3.3.4. Gap Analysis.....	41
3.4. Case Study 4 - FAIR-by-design national adaptation hub.....	42
3.4.1. Description.....	42
3.4.2. User Stories.....	43
3.4.3. FAIR Implementation Profile.....	47
3.4.4. Gap Analysis.....	49
3.5. Case Study 5 - Climate Connectivity Taxonomy, Hub and weADAPT.....	50
3.5.1. Description 5A - weADAPT.....	50
3.5.2. User Stories.....	51
3.5.3. Description 5B - Climate Connectivity Hub.....	51
3.5.3. FAIR Implementation Profile.....	53
3.5.4. Gap Analysis.....	53
3.6. Case Study 6 - FAIRification of a Climate Adaptation Strategy.....	55
3.6.1. Description.....	55
3.6.2. User Stories.....	56
3.6.3. FAIR Implementation Profile.....	58
3.6.4. Gap Analysis.....	59
4. Next Steps.....	60
4.1. Interrelationship between the case studies.....	60

4.2. FAIR Solution Demonstrators.....	61
4.3. Transfer Cases.....	62
4.4. From User Stories to Use Cases.....	62
4.5. Summary and Timeline.....	63
5. References.....	65
6. Annexes.....	66
List of figures.....	66
List of tables.....	66

F2A Draft

Glossary

TERM	DEFINITION
activity	the concrete, wished work to be conducted in a user story with one or more digital objects
action	an abstraction of the activity in a user story
actor	an agent (person, organization or software) acting in the environment investigated
aim	a broad, general vision an actor wants to achieve
archetype	a generalized, representative profile that captures the core behaviors, motivations and needs of an actor using a symbolic representation
benefit	the specific reason the user wants the functionality in a user story
case study	a description of a real-life situation where digital objects are used in practice
challenge	a potential or actual obstacle that requires a response or solution
community	a collection of actors who have a common objective
digital object	a digital resource
goal	a specific, long-term objective that contributes to the aim
action plan	a detailed description of required steps for fulfil specified requirements
needs	a high-level expectation by an actor in order to achieve a goal
purpose	an intended aim or rationale used to abstract benefits in user stories
responsibility	the set of regularly performed tasks and activities
role	an abstracted function of a user in a user story

TERM	DEFINITION
solution	a means of addressing, mitigating, or eliminating a challenge by applying an appropriate resource, method, or intervention
solution path	an approach giving a rough indication, which efforts are required to implement the solution
stakeholder	an actor that acts as a representative for an interest group
task	a concrete, clearly defined and achievable piece of work
use case	a usage scenario abstracted from a case study such that it can be generalised to other disciplines, systems or regions.
user	an actor in the context of a user story
user story	a statement that describes an action and its desired outcome from the perspective of a given user and breaks down requirements

Table 1: Glossary

Executive Summary

Aim of the Deliverable

- **Requirement elicitation:** To systematically identify and understand the goals, challenges and needs of potential users and stakeholders.
- **FAIR analysis:** To analyse the digital objects referenced in the user stories with respect to their FAIRification status and to extract representative variables from these digital objects
- **Solution paths:** To derive solution approaches from the identified requirements, forming the basis for the development of an action plan

Methodology

- User story driven requirement elicitation
- Systematic description of case studies, user stories and digital object analysis, represented and stored as RDF knowledge graphs.
- Qualitative assessment and gap analysis with FAIR Implementation Profiles, on which the quantitative FAIR assessment with FAIROS will build on
- Extraction of variables from the digital objects for future semantic modelling with I-Adopt service

Major Findings, Results, and Recommendations

- The case studies exhibit highly specific requirements as they address different levels of information processing and knowledge production.
- User-story centric approach to requirements elicitation proved effective in capturing these community-specific needs.

Limitations

- The deliverable provides an initial overview of case study requirements based on their current status.
- Further, more detailed analysis will be required in the second project year.

Conclusion of the Deliverable

- Prior to the requirements elicitation process, case study providers were trained in FAIR awareness and the creation of FAIR Implementation Profiles.
- This preparatory step significantly improved mutual understanding and facilitated more effective interactions throughout the requirements elicitation process.
- This capacity building will also be beneficial for the long-term implementation of FAIR practices within the case study communities.

1. Introduction

This deliverable focuses on requirement elicitation, a pre-phase of the FAIRification process that aims to identify the specific needs of stakeholders. In agile software development, requirements are used to identify functions or features, constraints, rules, or other elements that must exist to satisfy user needs (Cohn, 2004). A functional requirement defines what is needed, and not how it should be achieved (the solution). Non-functional requirements specify the criteria that will be used to test how well the solution meets the user's needs.

Gathering requirements to design the necessary services that the user expects is crucial, but is sometimes viewed as inefficient or overly restrictive when tried to be identified too early in the process because they can evolve over time. Thus, a more practical and tailored approach is needed for the FAIR2Adapt project to help bridge the gap between the different expectations of the case study providers (WP 6) on the one hand, and the technical experts (WP 2, 3, 4) on the other hand.

The FAIR2Adapt project is designed around six Climate Change Adaptation case studies (WP6) covering the six main steps defined by the Regional Adaptation Support Tool (RAST) to provide guidance to regional and local authorities during the adaptation planning process¹. The six case studies focus on: (1) Radionuclide distribution and environmental safety (Arctic), (2) Coastal water quality assessments (France), (3) Urban climate risk assessments (Hamburg, Germany), (4) Design of a national adaptation platform (Portugal), (5) Connecting and visualising the CCA knowledge landscape through the Connectivity Hub and weAdapt, and (6) FAIRification of a climate adaptation strategy (Germany).

Deliverable 5.2 is directly informed by activities and outputs from task 6.1, described in deliverable 6.1. In June 2025, the teams of task 6.1 and 5.2 conducted three-hour online workshops with stakeholders from each of the six case studies. While D6.1 documents the high level knowledge needs that shape adaptation decisions across the six case studies as a result of these workshops, D5.2 focuses on deriving concrete requirements to support the development of detailed action plans by the technical teams of WPs 2, 3 and 4.

The methodology chapter introduces the approach taken in FAIR2Adapt and outlines each of the required steps in the process. This chapter is followed by detailed analysis for each of the case studies' requirements by focusing on user stories and the analysis of the digital objects involved. The final chapter of this deliverable outlines the next steps that will take place in 2026.

1

<https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/knowledge-and-data/regional-adaptation-support-too>

2. Methodology

2.1. User story driven requirements

High-level requirements are often expressed in the form of a user story, which articulate needs from the perspective of an end-user and focus on the goal the user aims to achieve rather than on technical implementation details. This approach helps ensure that requirements remain user-centred, easily understandable by both stakeholders and technical teams, and suitable as a starting point for further refinement into more detailed and actionable specifications (Beck et al., 2001).

In FAIR2Adapt we apply user stories to identify the high-level FAIR requirements for each case study. We define a **case study** as a *description of a real-life situation involving several users and digital objects*. Hence, a case study can be broken down to a series of user stories (Fig. 1), which is reported from the perspective of a specific user.

Fig.1: Case Studies versus User Stories

A user story consists of three parts (see also definitions in the glossary):

Type of entry	As a ...	I want to...	so that...
Specific (text)	user	activity	benefit
Generalized (controlled list)	role	action	purpose

Table 2: Decomposition of a User Story

The three parts of a user story statement can be abstracted into more general terms to make them comparable to other user stories. In this way use cases can be generated to make them applicable to other disciplines, systems or regions.

Each activity is linked to one or more digital objects (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Case Studies, User Stories and Digital Objects

In most cases, these digital objects are far from being FAIR, and their level of FAIRness should be assessed using qualitative and quantitative methods.

2.2. FAIR analysis using FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP)

The FAIR Guiding Principles (Fig.3) are a set of criteria required to ensure that data and other research outputs are managed in a way that makes them easy to find, access, use, and reuse—by both humans and machines. FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (Wilkinson et al., 2016).. They were first articulated in 2016 and are widely cited in research, data management plans, and open science initiatives.

The FAIR Guiding Principles	
Findable:	
F1	Data and metadata are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
F2	Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
F3	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
F4	Data and metadata are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
Accessible:	
A1	Data and metadata are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
A1.1	The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
A1.2	The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
A2	Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
Interoperable:	
I1	Data and metadata use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
I2	Data and metadata use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
I3	Data and metadata include qualified references to other (meta)data
Reusable:	
R1	Data and metadata are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
R1.1	Data and metadata are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
R1.2	Data and metadata are associated with detailed provenance
R1.3	Data and metadata meet domain-relevant community standards

Fig. 3 The FAIR Guiding Principles

These principles describe the characteristics digital objects should have to enable machine actionability. The principles, however, do not come with concrete guidelines on how to achieve these requirements. To systematically address each of the FAIR Principles for enabling the

FAIRification of digital objects, the GO FAIR Foundation has developed the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) approach (Magagna et al., 2024).

A FIP is a structured questionnaire that documents relevant standards, technologies, and policies chosen by a community, made available as a collection of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs). The questionnaire asks for the resources used within a community to enable the various FAIR aspects addressed by the FAIR Principles for both metadata records and datasets. FAIR Principle R1.3 requires (meta)data that meet domain-relevant community standards. The FIP can be interpreted to document the collection of these community agreements and as such fulfilling R1.3 (Fig. 4).

FAIR principle	FIP Question	FAIR Enabling Resource type
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for metadata records?	Identifier service
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for datasets?	Identifier service
F2	Which metadata schemas do you use for findability?	Metadata schema
F3	What is the technology that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?	Metadata-Data linking schema
F4	In which search engines are your metadata records indexed?	Registry
F4	In which search engines are your datasets indexed?	Registry
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?	Communication protocol
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?	Communication protocol
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation technique do you use for metadata records?	Authentication & authorisation service
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation technique do you use for datasets?	Authentication & authorisation service
A2	Which metadata longevity plan do you use?	Metadata longevity
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?	Knowledge representation language
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?	Knowledge representation language
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?	Structured vocabularies
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?	Structured vocabularies
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your metadata records?	Metadata schema
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your datasets?	Data schema
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?	Data usage license
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your datasets?	Data usage license
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata	Provenance model
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?	Provenance model
R1.3	Who is the community, and what are their domain-relevant community standards?	The FAIR implementation Profile

Fig. 4 The core FIP questionnaire

In order to describe the resources used in a systematic way, a typology was developed and published as part of the FIP ontology². The main distinction is made between FAIR Enabling and FAIR Supporting Resources. While in this typology all resources are considered FAIR Supporting Resources (FSRs), only the FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) are considered to be essential for the fulfillment of the FAIR Principles. The resource types are broadly categorised as FAIR supporting technology, FAIR specification, FAIR data policy and FAIR practice. Fig. 5 shows the principles that can be addressed by these types.

² <https://w3id.org/fair/fip>

Next to the essential FERs addressing each of the principles, the FIP now also includes resources supporting the implementation of the FAIR Principles such as supporting interoperability specifications and services, formerly collected in a separate Semantic Interoperability Profile.

The Data Stewardship Wizard, initially developed as a data management planning (DMP) tool in ELIXIR (Hooft et al. 2016), is used as a compiler (the FIP Wizard³) for FIPs and their components, the FSRs. Knowledge models are used to craft questionnaires and integrations are used to embed FAIR vocabularies for selections of controlled answers. In addition, the FIP Wizard allows to represent the collected information as machine-readable output using JSON or RDF.

Fig. 5 The FAIR Supporting Resource Types

Nanopublications are used as the canonical representation for both FIPs and their resources. They are small RDF knowledge graphs, composed of an assertion and its provenance and publication metadata. Because they are persisted in the distributed nanopub server network and accessible via trustworthy and persistent URIs they are ideal for FAIR Digital Object compliant descriptions.

³ <https://fip.fair-wizard.com/>

FIP publication also encourages FIP reuse and repurposing by other communities, which saves time 'reinventing the wheel' and simultaneously drives convergence on FAIR implementation choices. FIPs and used FSRs can be searched in FAIR Connect⁴.

While compiling the FIP, the user is asked to select FSRs to document the current or planned use as agreed by the FAIR Implementation Community the user belongs to. In case the resource cannot be found, the user can create a new description with the same tool and then refer to it in the compilation of the FIP.

A FIP can be done for declaring the use of FSRs for different scopes:

- A. To document their general use within the community
- B. To document the recommendations as endorsed by the community
- C. To document their use within a specific case study
- D. To document their use for a specific digital object

In June 2025 each of the case studies published a FAIR Implementation Profile with scope C, and in September 2025 they published a Semantic Interoperability Profile for the same scope. Both declarations are now aggregated into single extended FIPs and serve as inputs for more specified FIPs for a specific digital object (scope D).

Because the documentation of the resources is based on RDF statements, all the information is queryable via SPARQL. This allows for analysis of the FIPs for different purposes. While the length of a FIP does not directly indicate its maturity, it can reveal where there are implementation gaps and which principles are not covered. Conclusions on what needs to be improved or developed can then be drawn from these gaps. Next to this analysis, comparisons with other FIPs might uncover potential overlaps and opportunities to converge with other related domains. Extensive use of these analysis capabilities has been undertaken by the ENVRI-FAIR and ITINERIS projects.

In FAIR2Adapt we go one step deeper and allow for a quantitative FAIR Assessment using FAIROS⁵ (Gonzalez et al., 2022) based on the F-UJI service⁶ but enriched with specific metrics (tests) tailored for the Climate Change Adaptation community. The FSRs collected in the FIPs will inform the FAIR Assessment service. This makes it an effective service to validate if the digital object actually implements the FSRs the community claims to use according to the FIP. In addition to providing the digital object with a FAIRness score, it indicates what needs to be addressed to improve its overall FAIRness. This will facilitate the development of a FAIRification plan, including the identification of required new FSR, such as metadata schemas or vocabularies.

⁴ <https://fairconnect.pro/search-fair-nanopublications/>

⁵ <https://fairos.readthedocs.io/>

⁶ <https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji>

Fig. 7: Processing phases in the requirement elicitation process

Processing steps by contributors

Inputs by case study providers:

- 1) Describe the *case study*
- 2) Describe the *user stories*
- 3) Link the case study to the user stories
- 4) Describe sample digital object involved (in the *digital object analysis* artefact)⁷
- 5) Link the user stories to the digital object analysis
- 6) Analyse sample digital object via *FIP*
- 7) Link digital object analysis to FIP

Inputs by technical experts:

- 8) FAIR assess based on FIPs
- 9) Derive FAIRification plans based on the assessment
- 10) Decide on required solution paths
- 11) Specify Action Plan based on the paths
- 12) Execute Action Plan

⁷ Because many data is often organized in data catalogues of the same digital object type, we refrain of describing single datasets, but instead we analyse sample digital objects representing them all in the artefact "Digital Object Analysis"

Inputs by semantic experts and LLM-enabled service:

- 13) Define variables aligned with I-ADOPT
- 14) Generalize user stories

And finally by technical experts:

- 15) Link to Solutions documented as FDO RO-Crates in RO-Hub

Information elements per artefact

The artefact is a FAIR bundle of triple RDF statements expressed as a nanopublication. In the following the predicates, the objects, the expected value types and the cardinalities are defined.

Case Study

Predicate	Object	Value type	Cardinality
http://purl.org/dc/terms/title	name	string	1..1
http://purl.org/dc/terms/description	description	string	1..1
https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/has-description-source	source of description	URL	0..1
https://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#contactPoint	contact point	ORCID	1..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/coordinated-by	lead partner	URL/ROR	1..1
https://schema.org/member	contributing partner	URL/ROR	0..n
https://w3id.org/fff/req/part-of-project	project name	string	1..n
http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#seeAlso	project website	URL	0..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/covers-domain	research domain	controlled list (research domain)	1..n
https://schema.org/spatialCoverage	geographical area	URL	1..n
https://schema.org/temporalCoverage	Temporal coverage	string	1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/has-goal	goal	string	1..n
https://w3id.org/fff/req/has-challenge	challenge	string	1..n
http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#seeAlso	more information	URL	0..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/hasUserStory	user story	URL (integration)	1..n

Table 3: Information elements of Case Studies

User Story

Predicate	Object	Value type	Cardinality
http://purl.org/dc/terms/title	name	string	1..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/as-a	user	string	1..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/has-role	role	controlled list (role)	1..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/i-want-to	activity	string	1..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/has-action	action	controlled list (action)	1..1
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfdesc#hasInput	digital object analysis	URL (integration)	1..n
https://w3id.org/fff/req/so-that	benefit	string	1..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/has-purpose	purpose	controlled list (purpose)	1..1
http://purl.org/wf4ever/wfdesc#hasOutput	digital object analysis	URL (integration)	0..n
http://purl.org/dc/terms/description	additional requirements	string	0..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/has-solution-path	solution path	controlled list (solution path)	1..n
https://w3id.org/fff/req/has-action-plan	action plan	URL	1..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/has-solution	solution	URL	1..1
http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#wasInformedBy	user story	URL (integration)	0..n

Table 4: Information elements of User Stories

The user story will therefore compile user requirements in natural language and their abstractions using controlled lists. It will also include **solution paths** and links to the **action plan**. The solution paths to choose from are:

- a. FAIRification
- b. Implementation of data processing pipeline
- c. Transformation of data to knowledge
- d. Implementation of dedicated dashboards
- e. Stakeholder engagement

The action plan comprises, depending on the solution paths chosen, the following plans respectively:

- a. A FAIRification plan, mainly driven by task 3.1
- b. A workflow plan, mainly driven by task 5.3
- c. A knowledge enrichment plan, mainly driven by task 4.2
- d. A dashboard plan, mainly driven by task 4.4

- e. A stakeholder engagement plan, mainly driven by task 6.1

The solution will be stored as FDO RO-Crates in RO-Hub:

- o The RO-Crate will be described with metadata defined via the CCA-specific RO-Crate Profile developed by WP 2.
- o The RO-Crate will contain all artefacts developed in the requirement elicitation process to document its provenance.

Digital object analysis

Predicate	Object	Value type	Cardinality
http://purl.org/dc/terms/title	name	string	1..1
http://purl.org/dc/terms/description	description	string	0..1
https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/has-description-source	source of description	URL	0..1
https://schema.org/identifier	Identifier of sample digital object	URL	0..1
https://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#contactPoint	contact point	ORCID	1..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/digital-object-type	digital object type	URL (integration)	1..n
https://w3id.org/fff/req/has-variable	variable	string	1..n
https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/#isDefinedBy	I-ADOPT variable	URL (integration)	1..n
https://w3id.org/fff/req/has-fip	FIP	URL (integration)	1..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/fair-assessment	FAIR assessment	URL	1..1
https://w3id.org/fff/req/fairification	FAIRification plan	URL	0..1

Table 5: Information elements of Digital Object Analysis

Variables as reported by the domain expert will be enriched with variable descriptions aligned with the I-ADOPT Framework (Magagna et al., 2022) using the I-ADOPT service in development by FAIR2Adapt in order to make the digital objects better findable in the ROHub.

FAIR Implementation Profile

A FAIR implementation is built by different elements:

- The FIP itself with its metadata
- The FIP index listing all FIP declarations
- The FIP declaration

Fig. 8: Elements of FAIR implementation

The FIP metadata are in summary represented as follows:

Predicate	Object	Value Type	Cardinality
http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#label	name	string	1..1
http://purl.org/dc/terms/description	description	string	0..1
https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/declared-by	FAIR Implementation Community	URL (integration)	1..1
https://schema.org/version	version	string	1..1
https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/declared-for-case-study	case study	URL (integration)	0..1
https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/declared-for-digital-object-type	digital object type	URL (integration)	0..n
https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/declared-for-sample-digital-object	sample digital object	URL	0..1
https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/has-declaration-index	fip-declaration-index	URL (integration)	1..1
FIP Declaration & FAIR Supporting Declaration			
https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/refers-to-question	question	URL (integration)	1..1
https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/declares-current-use-of OR https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/declares-planned-use-of OR https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/declares-planned-replacement-of	FAIR Supporting Resource	URL (integration)	1..1

Table 6: Information elements of FIP metadata

3. Case study specific requirements

The case study requirements were gathered in dedicated workshops with each of the case studies in June 2025 and in further follow up meetings. The results from these consultations must though be considered as preliminary and require ongoing efforts to achieve a full picture of the needs for each of the user stories collected and more specifically more in-depth analysis of involved digital objects. Moreover, additional user stories will be defined as considered useful and feasible to be addressed with the project’s timeline. The FIPs described have been collated by integrating both the FAIR Implementation Profile and the Semantic Interoperability Profile at the case study level into one comprehensive list. This will be the basis for more specialized FIPs at the sample digital object level to become a detailed understanding of the implementation gaps required to be addressed in the FAIRification plan.

Fig. 9: Integration of FIP and SIP

Nonetheless, in the following chapters the current status (December 2025) for each case study and their respective representations are reported following the previously described methodology.

3.1. Case Study 1 - Spread of radioactive isotopes in the Arctic under different climate scenarios

3.1.1. Case Study Description

- **Name:** F2A-CS1 | Spread of Radioactive Isotopes in the Arctic
- **URI:** https://w3id.org/np/RAg0_0HxISdUVibjSO57YG8mQR9uCYIU_L7msb_LkRVnM/F2A-CS1
- **Description:** Simulation of the spread of radioactive isotopes in the Arctic under different climate scenarios to assess the impacts of climate change on radionuclide distribution and implications for public and environmental safety. The climate crisis will potentially increase the discharge of radionuclide contamination as buried sources in the permafrost become active.
- **Contact Point:** <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5932-3627>
- **Lead Partner:** Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC)
- **Additional Partner:** Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP) Working Group of the Arctic Council
- **Research Domains:** Climate modelling, Earth System Science, Radiochemistry, Arctic research
- **Spatial coverage:** Norway, Canada, Sweden, Finland, US, Greenland, Russia, Denmark
- **Temporal coverage:** 2026-2027
- **Goals:**
 - Engagement of different groups of stakeholders: Members of AMAP Radioactivity Expert Group, scientific and technical partners, climate modelling community.
 - Make NorESM model predictions more easily accessible and useful for policy advisors and representatives of local governments.
 - Enable relevant stakeholders to understand climate change's impact on radionuclide distribution
- **Challenges:**
 - Difficulty for non-expert users to understand and reuse data for CCA. Reason: Data is dumped to the NIRD archive with minimal metadata; datasets have large size and are preserved in an unfamiliar - to the users - format.
 - Find and integrate different sources in the model and in the assessment of the concentration and distribution as observed.

3.1.2. User Stories

User Story F2A-CS1-US1 | Scientist integrates observations

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RADjt4J96oy1VBxHnaY_Yg0wBcjFwN1QImPX3RYwqYJ_Q/F2A-CS1-US1

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	scientist	integrate observations into the model	I can inform or constrain the model
generalized	researcher	integrate	constrain model

Table 7: User Story F2A-CS1-US1 | Scientist integrates observations

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA1 | Solar radiative forcing
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAL8py7oWtNu_xqLWp17h-FMCfn96RMUkdaH5Hc7TTbI0/F2A-CS1-DOA1
Type: Simulation Data
Variables: total solar irradiance, solar spectral irradiance, F10.7 index
- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA2 | Green-house concentrations
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAHy-LEI4ON3Gm7LK-cmpkzaiK_IdakMXmEt0pXK6IIac/F2A-CS1-DOA2
Type: Time-series data
Variables: carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide concentration
- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA3 | Ozone concentration
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAWGVZ9sq3kUMq6CvzdNwJqBqrSIhahmFvXGre3M3fw0/F2A-CS1-DOA3>
Type: Simulation data
Variables: ozone concentration
- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA4 | Emissions of short-lived species
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RA5NEft04ZtTzo9W1xgQteOdCNAkPolpFHqQoxUudO64/F2A-CS1-DOA4>
Type: Time series data
Variables: emissions of agricultural activity, transport, domestic heating, solvents; emissions from the energy and industrial sectors; aircraft emissions etc.
- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA5 | Water vapour emissions
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAD1b59koA6QMH4DJCwH2qQNM74jP8ys5w8OGilgFFcll/F2A-CS1-DOA5>
Type: Simulation data
Variables: production of H2O from methane oxidation
- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA6 | Stratospheric aerosol
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAvn4vK5wTOEtzqOydE_bQTUEH8tYClFqte6szky0c6gs/F2A-CS1-DOA6
Type: Simulation data
Variables: impact of volcanic SO2 emissions reaching the stratosphere and forming SO4 aerosol

- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA7 | Oxidant concentrations
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAh4JOIL8zHRCW6IWTmufyEyFKm-Xmrpn4QVkoagiukzw/F2A-CS1-DOA7>
Type: Sensor data
Variables: concentration of OH, ozone, NO3-radical, HO2; oxidation of DMS, SO2, isoprene and monoterpenes
- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA8 | Upper-ocean POM concentrations
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RA3nW-R_nNtjxnZxIOVpzYP0RdQq9mCteXNYBxNeEZ4QE/F2A-CS1-DOA8
Type: Simulation data
Variables: emission strength of marine primary organic matter from the ocean
- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA9 | Sea-surface temperature and sea-ice cover
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAD8M0oZZOk3di3Vh4d9_TG5i91OhHJR0CBBxIoBRCyIE/F2A-CS1-DOA9
Type: Simulation data
Variables: sea-surface temperature; sea-ice concentration

Solution path:

- FAIRification

User Story F2A-CS1-US2 | Scientist generates time-series data

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RA2vYzXEviwsANK2lwWZEgiYX14xamD_P1t0wczare2b0/F2A-CS1-US2

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	scientist	generates time series data of selected parameters via NORESM simulations	I can inform about tailored climate scenario outputs
generalized	researcher	generate	model scenario

Table 8: User Story F2A-CS1-US2 | Scientist generates time-series data

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA10 | NorESM Norwegian Earth System Model
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RApPCqA-KfhnUb1Ppysvzh1wcdYzuldb4jHN27yalUonw/F2A-CS1-DOA10>
Type: Computational Model
Variables: temperature, precipitation, cloud coverage in the atmosphere; currents, temperature, salinity in the ocean; vegetation on land; moisture and temperature in the soil; extent and thickness of snow and ice on land and at sea

Output Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA11 | NorESM model output
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAvJmshTmQ0H_w5diYILQja_ejbT4jU_oV8LAV_ltcqA/F2A-CS1-DOA11

Type: simulation data

Solution path:

- FAIRification
- Implementation of data processing pipeline

Builds upon user story: F2A-CS1-US1 | Scientist integrates information

User Story F2A-CS1-US3 | Scientist plots maps

URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAnGY3kBK24GQHCEnAML-eOngYSGZntq9vQe6fTj8vCA/F2A-CS1-US3>

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	scientist	plot maps of radioactive tracers	I can analyse the spread of radioactive tracers over the Arctic
generalized	researcher	visualize	assess impacts

Table 9: User Story F2A-CS1-US3 | Scientist plots maps

Input Digital Object(s):

- **Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA11 | NorESM model output
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAvfJmshTmQ0H_w5diYiLQja_ejbT4iU_oV8LAV_lTcQA/F2A-CS1-DOA11
Type: simulation data

Output Digital Object(s):

- **Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA12 | NorESM model plot
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RADoXLS2S8AEdKXecGo4TRwcl6AUqPmJtZmS5YA5oMOe4/F2A-CS1-DOA12>
Type: map

Solution path:

- Implementation of user-interactive dashboards
- Transformation of data to knowledge

Builds upon user story: F2A-CS1-US2 | Scientist generates time-series data

User Story F2A-CS1-US4 | Scientist provides interpretation

URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RANmLiwfmb8uDgQ2b6fPqL6kuF-fmpT0LNilsp-lmlzc/F2A-CS1-US4>

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	scientist	provide interpretation of the spread of radioactivity	I can inform stakeholders how to use the information
generalized	researcher	interpret	inform decisions

Table 10: User Story F2A-CS1-US4 | Scientist provides interpretation

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS1-DOA12 | NorESM model plot
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RADoXLS2S8AEdKXecGo4TRwcl6AUqPmJtZmS5YA5oMOe4/F2A-CS1-DOA12>
Type: map

Solution path:

- Implementation of user-interactive dashboards

Builds upon user story: F2A-CS1-US3 | Scientist plots maps

3.1.3. FAIR Implementation Profile

The following FIP was created for the case study but can only be considered a starting point for further application of the analysed digital objects.

URL: https://w3id.org/np/RAL70n6GhHNhcZ7UVi2r-69W4p_YN6oSbyk-sGx1ewhWo

Question	FSR Type	FAIR Supporting Resource (in grey: planned to be used)
F1 D	Identifier service for data	DataCite DOI Resolution Service
F2	Metadata schema	CKAN Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
F2	Metadata schema	DCAT Data Catalog Vocabulary Version 2
F2	Metadata schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
SF2-ME	Metadata editor service	ROHub Research Object Hub
SF2-VS	Validation service for metadata	FAIROS
F3	Metadata-data linking schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	NIRD-RDA NIRD Research Data Archive
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	ROHub Research Object Hub
F4 D	Registry for datasets	NIRD-RDA NIRD Research Data Archive

Deliverable 5.2 - User Requirements for FAIR and scientifically sound CCA [M3-M18]

A1.1 MD	Communication protocol for metadata	CSW Catalog Service for the Web
A1.1 MD	Communication protocol for metadata	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
A1.1 MD	Communication protocol for metadata	SPARQL (open) endpoint
A1.1 MD	Communication protocol for metadata	WFS Web Feature Service
A1.1 MD	Communication protocol for metadata	OAI-PMH Schema Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting Schema
A1.1 D	Communication protocol for datasets	CSW Catalog Service for the Web
A1.1 D	Communication protocol for datasets	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
A1.1 D	Communication protocol for datasets	WMS Web Map Service
A1.1 D	Communication protocol for datasets	WFS Web Feature Service
A1.1 D	Communication protocol for datasets	OAI-PMH Schema Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting Schema
A1.2 MD	Authentication & authorisation service for metadata	Open Data
A1.2 D	Authentication & authorisation service for datasets	Open Data
A2	Metadata preservation policy	DataCite DOI Policy
I1 MD	Knowledge representation language for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
I1 D	Knowledge representation language for datasets	NetCDF Network Common Data Form
SI1-FRS	FAIR representation service	Automated I-ADOPT Service
I2 MD	Structured vocabulary for metadata	CF SN Climate and Forecast Standard Names Parameter Vocabulary
I2 MD	Structured vocabulary for metadata	NVS NERC Vocabularies
I2 D	Structured vocabulary for datasets	CF SN Climate and Forecast Standard Names Parameter Vocabulary
SI2-ME	Editor for vocabulary creation	nanodash
I3 MD	Semantic model for metadata	I-ADOPT Framework
R1.1 MD	Data usage license for metadata	CC BY 4.0 Attribution 4.0 International
R1.1 D	Data usage license for datasets	CC BY 4.0 Attribution 4.0 International
R1.2 MD	Provenance model for metadata	PROV-O W3C PROV Ontology
R1.2 MD	Provenance model for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
R1.2 D	Provenance model for datasets	PROV-O W3C PROV Ontology
R1.3-FES	FAIR Enrichment Service	Automated I-ADOPT Service

Table 11: Basic FAIR Implementation Profile for Case Study 1

3.1.4. Gap Analysis

Although the FIP declares the use of DOIs for data, in many cases no persistent identifiers were found, at least not at the desired granularity level. Metadata records are missing identifiers and only provided for a few datasets. However, the registry NIRD Research Data Archive is a promising resource and the service providers are willing to go FAIR. In addition, the applied DCAT will be extended in alignment with the CCA ROHub profile which is currently developed within FAIR2Adapt. Regarding interoperability, so far CF standard names are used in NetCDF files for the variables. The I-ADOPT service is intended to be used when available to annotate the variables as machine-readable representations using NERC vocabularies as semantic resources.

3.2. Case Study 2 - RiOMar Project: Coastal Water Quality Anticipation to manage coastal zone ecosystem responses for biodiversity conservation

3.2.1. Description

- **Name:** F2A-CS2 | RiOMar
- **URI:** https://w3id.org/np/RALNrfJc3o4wTvUhsyKsVtGFbnFL_umfuThI_bj6H07u4/F2A-CS2
- **Description:** This case study aims to assess coastal water quality and marine ecosystem health in France while anticipating climate impacts expected by the end of the century. Using high-resolution outputs from the RiOMar model, it seeks to identify risks and vulnerabilities that can inform scientifically grounded climate-change adaptation strategies for coastal regions.
- **Contact Point:** <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1500-0156>
- **Lead Partner:** Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer (IFREMER)
- **Additional Partner:** Office Français de la Biodiversité (OFB); OCEANIS;
- **Research Domains:** Biochemistry; Physical Oceanography; Remote Sensing; Coastal Dynamics; Fluid Mechanics; Microbial Ecology; Ecology; Hydrology
- **Spatial coverage:** Hauts de France, Normandie, Bretagne, Pays de la Loire, Nouvelle Aquitaine, Occitanie, Provence Alpes Côte d'Azur, West Mediterranean Sea + Bay of Biscaye, Celtic Sea, English Channel
- **Temporal coverage:** 2022-2028
- **Goals**
 - to simulate the future of coastal ecosystems influenced by river inputs
 - to develop indicators in order to qualify the state of the environment (now and in the future)
 - to make RIOMAR's outputs available and usable by any entity willing to use these outputs
 - to provide environmental managers with useful information so as to develop management measures
- **Challenges:**
 - **Accessibility:** Stakeholders cannot easily access the large amounts of high-resolution data generated by RiOMar.
 - **Data availability:** Difficulties in developing indicators and thresholds to assess the vulnerability of coastal zone ecosystems to climate change due to a lack of past (FAIRified) data.
 - **Usability:** Difficulties in finding easily usable operational FAIRification-tools and finding relevant information in their native language (French).

3.2.2. User Stories

User Story F2A-CS2-US1 | Data Manager optimizes workflow

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAuWuxIsKTghrDsehFCf8oGVLr7Ztd2BY_m3bnzGLE_4/F2A-CS2-US1

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	Data manager	optimize the workflow for publishing and curating RIOMar data	access and selection on user platforms based on variables, geographical and time range is fast and easy for the scientist
generalized	Data steward	streamline	optimize processes

Table 12: User Story F2A-CS2-US1 | Data manager optimizes workflow

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS2-DOA1 | RioMar In-situ moorings
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAUlf4C01AHMdenR3GhGXEnNNquKKCAkDLg-2auDpPbCM/F2A-CS2-DOA1>
Type: Time-series data; In-Situ Measurement
Variables: mean sea level pressure
- Name:** F2A-CS2-DOA3 | RioMar Scenario runs
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RArV3Te8KcDWK02hkqnyZrLBDOq_-ovj_aloerPoFISk/F2A-CS2-DOA3
Type: time-series data; simulation data

Output Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS2-DOA2 | RioMar Hindcast
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAuRCFav2YI_LLGMIoXR8Nq53pKzD4bgB8ZpLBOZziYno/F2A-CS2-DOA2
Type: time-series data; simulation data
Variables: water level; water current; water temperature; salinity; bed substrate composition

Solution path:

- Implementation of data processing pipeline

User Story F2A-CS2-US2 | Policy maker select variables

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RA57TL0dv2PxzwUZWaGMRbbpk3TbjFhtMiUJ89da_gYA/F2A-CS2-US2

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	Policy maker	define scenarios setting different ranges of input variables	simulations can be run based on them
generalized	Policy maker	define	Model scenario

Table 13: User Story F2A-CS2-US2 | Policy maker select variables

Solution path:

- Stakeholder engagement
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard

Builds upon user story: F2A-CS2-US1 | Data Manager optimize workflow

User Story F2A-CS2-US3 | Researcher configures scenario

URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAagJ87VzHDumWw7WTnPhonTXrOQBCrV7vKkMj5ZVJh-0/F2A-CS2-US3>

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	researcher	Configure simulations based on the scenarios and existing data	I can calculate simulation data.
generalized	researcher	configure	model scenario

Table 14: User Story | Researcher configures scenario

Input Digital Object(s):

- **Name:** F2A-CS2-DOA1 | RioMar In-situ moorings
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAUlf4C01AHMdenR3GhGXEnNNguKKCAkDLq-2auDpPbCM/F2A-CS2-DOA1>
Type: time-series data; in-situ measurement
Variables: mean sea level pressure
- **Name:** F2A-CS2-DOA2 | RioMar Hindcast
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAuRCFav2YI_LLGMIoXR8Ng53pKzD4bgB8ZpLBOZziYno/F2A-CS2-DOA2
Type: time-series data; simulation data
Variables: water level; water current; water temperature; salinity; bed substrate composition
- **Name:** F2A-CS2-DOA4 | RioMar Biologging fish tracks
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAp3iT7yWBEqYOexR9IUYVlojlr2W2ldzkWsKqnaVuT7o/F2A-CS2-DOA4>
Type: time-series data

Output Digital Object(s):

- **Name:** F2A-CS2-DOA3 | RioMar Scenario runs
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RArV3Te8KcDWK02hkqnyZrLBDOq_-ovj_aloerPoFISk/F2A-CS2-DOA3
Type: time-series data; simulation data

Solution path:

- Stakeholder engagement
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard

Builds upon user story: F2A-CS2-US2 | Policy maker select variables

User Story F2A-CS2-US4 | Policy maker develops measures

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAnoJcmnjWBI3gu2adlNos_oGXCfio_Ae4gF128_4nc/F2A-CS2-US4

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	Policy maker	use modelled scenarios	I can develop measures
generalized	Policy maker	find	provide recommendations

Table 15: User Story | Policy maker develops measures

Input Digital Object(s):

- **Name:** F2A-CS2-DOA3 | RioMar Scenario runs
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RArV3Te8KcDWK02hkqnyZrLBDOq_oj_aloerPoFISk/F2A-CS2-DOA3
Type: time-series data; simulation data

Solution path:

- Stakeholder engagement
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard

Builds upon user story: F2A-CS2-US3 | Researcher configures scenario

User Story F2A-CS2-US5 | Data analyst develops success indicators

URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RASKW9X1ezQSljbDpasl3JwXgWkPGjKG2g9MMcebceKc0/F2A-CS2-US5>

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	Data analyst	Develop success indicators for CCA measures	the efficiency decisions taken can be evaluated
generalized	Data analyst	generate	Evaluate outcomes

Table 16: User Story | Data analyst develops success indicators

Output Digital Object(s):

- **Name:** F2A-CS2-DOA3 | RioMar Scenario runs
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RArV3Te8KcDWK02hkqnyZrLBDOq_oj_aloerPoFISk/F2A-CS2-DOA3
Type: time-series data; simulation data

Solution path:

- Stakeholder engagement
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard

Builds upon user story: F2A-CS2-US4 | Policy maker develops measures

3.2.3. FAIR Implementation Profile

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAs6_kCEos5itKDnH7AXodfNwRCzEN5Gr-MJU6Zwe_kb8

Question	FSR Type	FAIR Supporting Resource (in grey: planned to be used)
F1 D	Identifier service for data	DOI Digital Object Identifier
F2	Metadata schema	ISO 19115 Geographic information - Metadata
F2	Metadata schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
SF2-ME	Metadata editor service	ROHub Research Object Hub
F3	Metadata-data linking schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	SEANOE - SEA scieNtific Open data Edition
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	NIRD-RDA NIRD Research Data Archive
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	ROHub Research Object Hub
F4 D	Registry for datasets	SEANOE - SEA scieNtific Open data Edition
A1.1 MD	Communication protocol for metadata	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
A1.1 D	Communication protocol for datasets	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
A1.2 MD	Authentication & authorisation service for metadata	Open Data
A1.2 D	Authentication & authorisation service for datasets	Open Data
I1 MD	Knowledge representation language for metadata	eXtensible Markup Language (XML)
I1 MD	Knowledge representation language for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
I1 D	Knowledge representation language for datasets	NetCDF Network Common Data Form
SI1-FRS	FAIR representation service	Automated I-ADOPT Service
I2 MD	Structured vocabulary for metadata	NVS NERC Vocabularies
I2 D	Structured vocabulary for datasets	CF SN Climate and Forecast Standard Names Parameter Vocabulary
I3 MD	Semantic model for metadata	ISO 19115 Geographic information - Metadata
I3 MD	Semantic model for metadata	I-ADOPT Framework
I3 D	Semantic model for datasets	OceanSITES OceanSITES Data Format
R1.1 MD	Data usage license for metadata	CC BY 4.0 Attribution 4.0 International
R1.1 D	Data usage license for datasets	CC BY 4.0 Attribution 4.0 International
R1.2 MD	Provenance model for metadata	ISO 19115 Geographic information - Metadata
R1.2 MD	Provenance model for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate

R1.2 D	Provenance model for datasets	ISO 19115 Geographic information - Metadata
R1.3-FES	FAIR Enrichment Service	Automated I-ADOPT Service

Table 17: Basic FAIR Implementation Profile for Case Study 2

3.2.4. Gap Analysis

Although the FIP declares the use of DOIs for datasets, no identifier service is declared for metadata records, limiting citability and reference stability for metadata. The FIP currently lacks a metadata-data linking schema and a metadata validation service, though the intended use of RO-Crate will address the linking gap and FAIROS integration will enable automated FAIR assessment. No metadata preservation policy is declared, which should be established through SEANOE or another trusted repository. Regarding interoperability, the case study benefits from established marine data standards including ISO 19115 for metadata schemas and CF Standard Names with NERC vocabularies for dataset encoding. However, no FAIR representation service is currently in use. The I-ADOPT service is intended to be used when available to annotate oceanographic variables as machine-readable representations. The planned transformation of RiOMar model outputs to Analysis Ready Cloud Optimised (ARCO) data formats and integration with Pangeo@EOSC and STAC catalogues will significantly improve accessibility and usability for stakeholders including the French Biodiversity Office and regional aquaculture managers.

3.3. Case Study 3 - Hamburg City: Climate-induced stressors and their effects on urban societies

3.3.1. Description

- **Name:** F2ACS3 | CS3 Risk Index for City of Hamburg
- **URI:**
- **Description:** This case study develops a high-resolution risk index by integrating hazard modeling, exposure assessment, and social vulnerability analysis within the IPCC risk framework, and applies it to Hamburg, Northern Germany.
- **Contact Point:** <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3300-7482>
- **Lead Partner:** University of Hamburg
- **Additional Partner:** Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg Senate Chancellery; Landesbetrieb Geoinformation und Vermessung;
- **Research Domains:** Urban Planning; Environmental Science; Water Management; Geography; Social Science; Climate Risk
- **Spatial Coverage:** City of Hamburg (Germany)
- **Temporal Coverage:** 2025-2027
- **Goals:**
 - to understand climate-induced stressors and their effects on urban societies
 - to be prepared for future climate risks of the city of Hamburg
 - to inform sustainable climate change adaptation strategies
 - to transfer knowledge to planners of other cities
 - to improve current risk assessment practices in Germany by providing a more integrated and holistic approach (through the combination of pluvial flood hazard data with data of exposure and social vulnerability of the urban population)
- **Challenges:**
 - Data related to climate-induced stressors are often not updated.
 - Cities use different data portals - and do not utilise European or global data portals (e.g. Copernicus).
 - Data is presented in different formats in different cities.

3.3.2. User Stories

User Story F2A-CS3-US1 | Researcher shares tool

URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAFunore3A4GortCHYC-qjywXmHSvbcvNexVs1pIENS DU/F2A-CS3-US1>

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	researcher	share the Hamburg Risk Map ArcGIS tool	it is transferrable to other regions
generalized	researcher	share	transfer knowledge

Table 18: User Story F2A-CS3-US1 | Researcher shares tool

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS3-DOA1 | Riskmap toolbox
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAi18HixAA7sBYNkDpymJiBVnydG0HW08AnO6YNoVIV6c/F2A-CS3-DOA1>
Type: software
Variables: hazard index for mobility and accessibility; hazard index for wellbeing; pluvial flood risk to mobility and accessibility; pluvial flood risk to well-being;
- Name:** F2A-CS3-DOA5 | Paper on High-Resolution Framework on Pluvial Flood Risk
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAa7CAHcYUBuhX-c4RypESn-LxVO4E-3JjJRNf7XU6-2s/F2A-CS3-DOA5>
Type: scientific literature
Variables: hazard index for mobility and accessibility; hazard index for wellbeing; pluvial flood risk to mobility and accessibility; pluvial flood risk to well-being;

Solution path:

- FAIRification
- Implementation of data processing pipeline
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard

User Story F2A-CS3-US2 | Researcher integrates data

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RA_BP5GFxpbUoPjv18bvl_s2NFQbkD0QMLCLoMMwIPhyU/F2A-CS3-US2

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	researcher	integrate data on exposure, social vulnerability and simulated data on pluvial flood	I can calculate pluvial flood risk
generalized	researcher	integrate	identify vulnerabilities

Table 19: User Story F2A-CS3-US2 | Researcher integrates data

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS3-DOA1 | Riskmap toolbox
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAi18HixAA7sBYNkDpymJiBVnydG0HW08AnO6YNoVIV6c/F2A-CS3-DOA1>
Type: software
Variables: hazard index for mobility and accessibility; hazard index for wellbeing; pluvial flood risk to mobility and accessibility; pluvial flood risk to well-being;
- Name:** F2A-CS3-DOA2 | Hamburg Flood data
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RASXGwzaMlyjwko8brTy1EHChpZ96IG1eU3ru9EIGXssY/F2A-CS3-DOA2>
Type: simulation data
Variables: Water level based on pluvial flood scenario based on a rainfall of 36 mm/h reflecting a 100-year event

- Name:** F2A-CS3-DOA3 | Hamburg Population Data
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAzj9GOnZnnKG2l01oY99HF32UYUI-PRG3ROfKCs26m8/F2A-CS3-DOA3>
Type: statistical data
Variables: residents per building; receivers of welfare; number of residents without high school diploma within the last 3 years; number of singles being older than 65 years; number of children being younger than 10 years;
- Name:** F2A-CS3-DOA6 | Infrastructure data
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RATmXvplQTpEo34ntjZUA_Tliaya8ZDb0Q4C74VAS4_0Y/F2A-CS3-DOA6
Type: spatial data
Variables: number of floors above ground level; type of building; street distribution

Output Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS3-DOA7 | Pluvial Flood Risk
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAD7kRqg9ogBEUY3YibreNMYIWRearTsKNO2cM2_ru6w/F2A-CS3-DOA7
Type: spatial data
Variables: hazard index for mobility and accessibility; hazard index for wellbeing; pluvial flood risk to mobility and accessibility; pluvial flood risk to well-being;

Solution path:

- FAIRification

Builds upon user story: F2A-CS3-US1 | Researcher shares tool

User Story F2A-CS3-US3 | Researcher makes paper machine-processable

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RASmsYy_0HCEHDCTV3yltf_7fj1g2Q1sLqQ2f9IKfPcmg/F2A-CS3-US3

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	researcher	make scientific knowledge and findings in my paper machine-processable	I can make my calculations reproducible
generalized	researcher	transform	share information

Table 20: User Story F2A-CS3-US3 | Researcher makes paper machine-processable

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS3-DOA2 | Hamburg Flood data
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RASXGwzaMlyjwko8brTy1EHChpZ96IG1eU3ru9EIGXssY/F2A-CS3-DOA2>
Type: simulation data
Variables: Water level based on pluvial flood scenario based on a rainfall of 36 mm/h reflecting a 100-year event
- Name:** F2A-CS3-DOA4 | Paper on Urban Pluvial Flood Risk Mapping
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAz0KQXyKnMABJSAwUqrPicgbNAL9IaVrkKaztqQP25uE/F2A-CS3-DOA4>

Type: scientific literature

Variables: hazard index for mobility and accessibility; hazard index for wellbeing; pluvial flood risk to mobility and accessibility; pluvial flood risk to well-being;

Solution path:

- FAIRification
- Transformation of Data to Knowledge

3.3.3. FAIR Implementation Profile

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RA-yTGAt_3bzIQbRri2abQ7HwJVr6gr5QS5g9mnAH1fYE

Question	FSR Type	FAIR Supporting Resource (in grey: planned to be used)
F1 MD	Identifier service for metadata	DOI Digital Object Identifier
F1 D	Identifier service for data	DOI Digital Object Identifier
F2	Metadata schema	DataCite Metadata Schema v4.4
F2	Metadata schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
SF2-ME	Metadata editor service	ROHub Research Object Hub
SF2-VS	Validation service for metadata	FAIROS
F3	Metadata-data linking schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	ROHub Research Object Hub
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	Zenodo
F4 D	Registry for datasets	Zenodo
A1.1 MD	Communication protocol for metadata	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
A1.1 D	Communication protocol for datasets	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
A1.2 MD	Authentication & authorisation service for metadata	Open Data
A1.2 D	Authentication & authorisation service for datasets	Open Data
A2	Metadata preservation policy	Metadata preservation policy: ZMPP Zenodo metadata preservation policy
I1 MD	Knowledge representation language for metadata	JSON-LD JavaScript Object Notation for Linking Data
I1 MD	Knowledge representation language for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
I1 D	Knowledge representation language for datasets	ASCII American Standard Code for Information Interchange
S11-FRS	FAIR representation service	ORKG Open Research Knowledge Graph
S11-FRS	FAIR representation service	Automated I-ADOPT Service

I2 MD	Structured vocabulary for metadata	CodeMeta
I3 MD	Semantic model for metadata	I-ADOPT Framework
R1.1 MD	Data usage license for metadata	CC BY 4.0 Attribution 4.0 International
R1.2 MD	Provenance model for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
R1.3-FES	FAIR Enrichment Service	Automated I-ADOPT Service

Table 21: Basic FAIR Implementation Story for Case Study 3

3.3.4. Gap Analysis

The FIP shows clearly the need to go FAIR, as the case study currently does not make use of FAIR Enabling Resources. Nevertheless, the case study providers expressed a strong willingness to adopt the project's resources to improve the FAIR level of their digital objects. This will involve migrating the proprietary GIS tool to open source environments like Python, which makes geospatial workflows more efficient, scalable, and reproducible and the application of the FAIR for Research Software recommendations. The ORKG technology will be used to FAIRify the scientific knowledge presented in their scientific paper. This will ensure that the scientific findings are also made available in machine-readable and reproducible form. FAIRifying the input data for the calculation of the Pluvial Flood Risk is expected to substantially enhance the applicability and transferability of the risk assessment framework to other urban environments.

3.4. Case Study 4 - Developing and testing a FAIR-by-design national adaptation hub

3.4.1. Description

- **Name:** F2A-CS4 | Portugal National Hub
- **URI:** https://w3id.org/np/RAcpgwRnEyaVs3lczfYVIR0CWVjGegguR_RtR1ymUSM8w/F2A-CS4
- **Description:** Design of FAIR-by-design national climate change adaptation platform for Portugal
- **Contact Point:** <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8796-5993>
- **Lead Partner:** FCIênciasID
- **Research Domain:** Atmospheric Science, Meteorology, Biodiversity, Urban Planning, Biology, Ecology, Agronomy, Hydrogeology, Oceanography, Political Science, Human Geography, Social Science, Geophysics, Economics, Environmental Science, Hydrology
- **Spatial coverage:** Portugal
- **Temporal coverage:** 2025-
- **Goals:**
 - to make the wide range of resources relevant for national-to-local adaptation planning (e.g., scientific and grey literature, datasets, policy documentation, knowledge platforms) easily accessible
 - to develop a platform that contains climate adaptation-relevant resources and make it available to adaptation actors in Portugal
 - to apply, in practice, the FAIR2Adapt approach to design Portugal's first National Adaptation Hub, and test its relevance for adaptation policy decision-making process at multiple scales
- **Challenges:**
 - Access: relevant actors, from national to local level, require access to large amounts of data and knowledge to build resilience to climate change in Portugal.
 - Confusion: A profusion of national and regional adaptation portals, platforms and other initiatives aiming to support policymakers and practitioners in their adaptation planning has led to confusion amongst users about good practice and what is relevant, salient and credible information.
 - Findability: There is already a substantial body of scientific outputs, policy documents, datasets, and grey literature, yet many of these resources remain difficult to find or access for the diverse community involved in climate adaptation.

3.4.2. User Stories

User Story F2A-CS4-US1 | Researcher shares resources

URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RA3ZbYz71d3WJPlx2HO2WnurRdSOmslZL2lQAd2Bsntns/F2A-CS4-US1>

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	researcher	create and/or share datasets, scripts and metadata together with the scientific paper	other actors can use it and create new knowledge
generalized	researcher	share	transfer information

Table 22: User Story F2A-CS4-US1 | Researcher shares resources

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA2 | Portal do Clima
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAEgE_Ms8ozbIDXFghdul-gbKPC7pPqGv4EUedPLdpDho/F2A-CS4-DOA2
Type: Database
Variables: Minimum, maximum and mean air temperature; number of heatwave days; number of very cold days; number of tropical nights; thermic amplitudes;
- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA3 | Research Article
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RArlaRmyEyr5PoCgNPGHTR_nJQROHWI6IMJkWwLVQtpA/F2A-CS4-DOA3
Type: Article
- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA4 | Statistics Portugal
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RA4-AB6HxAle2_GuU0r_PPuX41-oL5QU74ujPzQ9RtDTg/F2A-CS4-DOA4
Type: Database
Variables: annual mean net income (€) per household; resident population per year, per NUTS, by sex and age group; severe housing deprivation rate (%) by age group, annually;

Solution path:

- FAIRification
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard
- Transformation of data to knowledge

User Story F2A-CS4-US2 | Private companies access policy

URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RA3vNqE0TD3Q5d9ML5No-MrSf1RkJzc-9DJZt38MxgDc/F2A-CS4-US2>

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
consultants, companies, advisors	consultants, companies, advisors	have access to policy and regulatory frameworks on user-friendly and machine readable platforms	I can propose measures for climate change adaptation
generalized	consultant	access	provide recommendations

Table 23: User Story F2A-CS4-US2 Private companies access policy

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA1 | Policy
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAkgjmBT6XKUhcKigTE8gD4b1a5Qgk6WC7ZIQjThrTdA/F2A-CS4-DOA1>
Type: Policy document
- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA3 | Research Article
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RArIaRmyEvr5PoCgNPGHTR_nJQROHWI6IMJkVwLVQtpA/F2A-CS4-DOA3
Type: Article

Solution path:

- FAIRification
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard
- Transformation of data to knowledge

Builds upon User Story: F2A-CS4-US1 | Researcher shares resources

User Story F2A-CS4-US3 | NGO officer produces studies

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAgExFNu2z_CsLCODIqyWR8jptFGawOj8hbGdZCSbtGIU/F2A-CS4-US3

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	Data and Knowledge Producer	Engage with science-policy-society interface	I push for climate action
generalized	NGO officer	engage	raise awareness

Table 24: User Story F2A-CS4-US3 | NGO officer produces studies

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA1 | Policy
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAkgjmBT6XKUhcKigTE8gD4b1a5Qgk6WC7ZIQjThrTdA/F2A-CS4-DOA1>

Type: Policy document

- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA2 | Portal do Clima
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAEgE_Ms8ozbIDXFghdul-gbKPC7pPqGv4EUedPLdpDho/F2A-CS4-DOA2
Type: Database
Variables: Minimum, maximum and mean air temperature; number of heatwave days; number of very cold days; number of tropical nights; thermic amplitudes;
- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA3 | Research Article
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RArIaRmyEyr5PoCgNPGHTR_nJQROHWI6IMJkWwLVQtpA/F2A-CS4-DOA3
Type: Article
- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA4 | Statistics Portugal
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RA4-AB6HxAle2_GuU0r_PPuX41-oL5QU74ujPzQ9RtDTg/F2A-CS4-DOA4
Type: database
Variables: annual mean net income (€) per household; resident population per year, per NUTS, by sex and age group; severe housing deprivation rate (%) by age group, annually;
- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA5 | Adapt.local
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAoSzLdVYmV7XVSdqba2qjMSjifTsNwu5aaDjVOxlsCUg/F2A-CS4-DOA5>
Type: website

Solution path:

- FAIRification
- Transformation of data to knowledge
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard

Builds upon User Story: F2A-CS4-US1 | Researcher shares resources

User Story F2A-CS4-US4 | Policy owner finds information

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAFGqjhs66hfzKN8huduD9zDOuv_YMZyoz1uGyKPaoLy0/F2A-CS4-US4

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	Policy owner - National Level Executive	receive reliable information	I can improve existing policies by incorporating this knowledge.
generalized	central government representative	integrate	influence policy

Table 25: User Story F2A-CS4-US4 | Policy owner finds information

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA1 | Policy
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAkgjmBT6XKUhcKigTE8gD4b1a5Qggk6WC7ZIQiThrTdA/F2A-CS4-DOA1>
Type: Policy document
- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA2 | Portal do Clima
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAEgE_Ms8ozbIDXfghdul-gbKPC7pPqGv4EUedPLdpDho/F2A-CS4-DOA2
Type: Database
Variables: Minimum, maximum and mean air temperature; number of heatwave days; number of very cold days; number of tropical nights; thermic amplitudes;
- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA3 | Research Article
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RArlaRmyEyr5PoCgNPGHTR_nJQROHWI6IMJkWwLVQtpA/F2A-CS4-DOA3
Type: Article
- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA4 | Statistics Portugal
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RA4-AB6HxAle2_GuU0r_PPuX41-oL5QU74ujPzQ9RtDTg/F2A-CS4-DOA4
Type: Database
Variables: annual mean net income (€) per household; resident population per year, per NUTS, by sex and age group; severe housing deprivation rate (%) by age group, annually;

Solution path:

- FAIRification
- Transformation of data to knowledge
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard

Builds upon User Stories: F2A-CS4-US1 | Researcher shares resources; F2A-CS4-US2 | Private companies access policy; F2A-CS4-US3 | NGO officer produces studies

User Story F2A-CS4-US5 | Municipal executives find relevant information

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAPVZruF_ILkwrwzT2GR9NiTBqUll-bjfPoM7t9Mqie_4/F2A-CS4-US5

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	Municipal executives	find processed data	include the knowledge in decision making process, policy proposal and adoption
generalized	local government representative	find	inform decisions

Table 26: User Story F2A-CS4-US5 | Municipal executives find relevant information

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA2 | Portal do Clima
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAEgE_Ms8ozbIDXFghdul-gbKPC7pPqGv4EUedPLdpDho/F2A-CS4-DOA2
Type: Database
Variables: Minimum, maximum and mean air temperature; number of heatwave days; number of very cold days; number of tropical nights; thermic amplitudes;
- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA3 | Research Article
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RARlaRmyEvr5PoCgNPGHTR_nJQROHWI6IMJkWwLVQtpA/F2A-CS4-DOA3
Type: Article
- Name:** F2A-CS4-DOA4 | Statistics Portugal
URI: https://w3id.org/np/RA4-AB6HxAle2_GuU0r_PPuX41-oL5QU74ujPzQ9RfDTg/F2A-CS4-DOA4
Type: database
Variables: annual mean net income (€) per household; resident population per year, per NUTS, by sex and age group; severe housing deprivation rate (%) by age group, annually;

Solution path:

- FAIRification
- Transformation of data to knowledge
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard

Builds upon User Stories: F2A-CS4-US1 | Researcher shares resources; F2A-CS4-US2 | Private companies access policy; F2A-CS4-US3 | NGO officer produces studies

3.4.3. FAIR Implementation Profile

URL: https://w3id.org/np/RARzgoSAH025B16jowGX3c_QKfzkqJN1jWK33bXN1TxMM

Question	FSR Type	FAIR Supporting Resource (in grey: planned to be used)
F1 MD	Identifier service for metadata	DOI Digital Object Identifier
F1 D	Identifier service for datasets	DOI Digital Object Identifier
F2	Metadata schema	Crossref (DOI)
F2	Metadata schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
SF2-ME	Metadata editor service	ROHub Research Object Hub
SF2-VS	Validation service for metadata	FAIROS
F3	Metadata-data linking schema	DOI Digital Object Identifier
F3	Metadata-data linking schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	Scopus
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	ROHub Research Object Hub

Deliverable 5.2 - User Requirements for FAIR and scientifically sound CCA [M3-M18]

F4 D	Registry for datasets	Scopus
A1.1 MD	Communication protocol for metadata	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
A1.1 D	Communication protocol for datasets	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
A1.2 MD	Authentication & authorisation service for metadata	Open Data
A1.2 D	Authentication & authorisation service for datasets	Open Data
A1.2 D	Authentication & authorisation service for datasets	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
A2	Metadata preservation policy	DataCite DOI Policy
I1 MD	Knowledge representation language for metadata	Portable Document Format (PDF)
I1 MD	Knowledge representation language for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
I1 D	Knowledge representation language for datasets	Portable Document Format (PDF)
S11-FRS	FAIR representation service	ORKG Open Research Knowledge Graph
S11-FRS	FAIR representation service	Automated I-ADOPT Service
I2 MD	Structured vocabulary for metadata	Climate Change Adaptation Taxonomy
I2 D	Structured vocabulary for datasets	Climate Change Adaptation Taxonomy
I3 MD	Semantic model for metadata	I-ADOPT Framework
I3 D	Semantic model for datasets	I-ADOPT Framework
R1.1 MD	Data usage license for metadata	CC BY 4.0 Attribution 4.0 International
R1.1 D	Data usage license for datasets	CC BY 4.0 Attribution 4.0 International
R1.2 MD	Provenance model for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
R1.3-FES	FAIR Enrichment Service	Automated I-ADOPT Service

Table 25: Basic FAIR Implementation Profile for Case Study 4

3.4.4. Gap Analysis

Although the FIP declares the use of DOIs for data, in many cases no persistent identifiers were found. Structured metadata is often lacking and missing identifiers. Scopus, used for registry of datasets as well as metadata, is not open, limiting findability of metadata. The intended use of RO-crates as metadata schema, data-metadata linking schema, and provenance model, as well as metadata registry in ROHub, are very promising for FAIRification. Access to data is open where possible, but in some cases restricted to non-machine actionable access upon request. While the use of PDF is still declared, the intended use of ORKG is very promising for FAIRification of datasets. As for Metadata, the I-ADOPT service is intended to be used when available to annotate the variables as machine-readable representations using the Climate Change Adaptation Taxonomy as semantic resource.

3.5. Case Study 5 - Connecting and visualising the CCA knowledge landscape through the Climate Connectivity Taxonomy, Hub and weADAPT

3.5.1. Description 5A - weADAPT

- **Name:** F2A CS5A
- **URI:** https://w3id.org/np/RARmEtdbSrww6pl1xpF-S8bFaEF_Jqo2oTiAaXNIEy9_k/F2A-CS5A
- **Description:** weADAPT is a global online knowledge-sharing platform designed to improve access to climate adaptation information, widely used amongst researchers, practitioners and decision-makers. Knowledge on the platform is organized around +25 themes and networks, and the platform also uses keywords to enhance discoverability. This project aims to make climate adaptation knowledge more accessible, discoverable, and usable by developing improved taxonomies and knowledge graphs.
- **Contact Point:** <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0152-4565>
- **Lead Partner:** Stockholm Environment Institute
- **Research Domains:** Climate Change Adaptation, Climate Risk, Environmental Science, Education Science, Geology, Geography, Earth System Science, Social Science
- **Spatial Coverage:** global
- **Temporal Coverage:** 2026-2027
- **Goals:**
 - Improve weADAPT to support communities, planners, practitioners, students, researchers and policymakers in accessing and sharing climate-resilient adaptation information and strategies
 - Break down silos and avoid redundancy, replication, and wasted resources while promoting collaboration, dialogue, and learning, by harnessing the wealth of existing knowledge across various portals, platforms, and publications, and providing guidance on how to connect this knowledge together.
 - Integrate weADAPT in EOSC. Ensure that climate adaptation knowledge is accessible within EOSC, increasing its usability for a broad range of stakeholders.
- **Challenges:**
 - Scientific and policy information often struggles to match the pace, language, and trust-building needed for genuine co-creation.
 - Difficulty of structuring diverse knowledge in a way that retains meaning across scales and contexts.
 - Difficulty of providing knowledge in a harmonised way.

3.5.2. User Stories

User Story 1 (CS5A)

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAxYOWwW3eHAOL1JbbP6rO6ejo_LT68aWawpaWKPUbCuM/F2A-CS5A-US1

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	Platform manager	Reorganize and revisualize content	understand the landscape
generalized	Infrastructure manager	optimize	raise awareness

Table 27: User Story F2A-CS5-US1

Input Digital Object(s):

- **Name:** F2A-CS5A-DOA1 | WeADAPT
- **URI:** https://w3id.org/np/RAARjjDzjRGjPrxa-_7fXT_sbhQ8BhJ4_tP0yFODr5Q80/F2A-CS5A-DOA1
- **Type:** Registry
- **Variables:** Climate Change related variables

Input Digital Object(s):

- **Name:** F2A-CS5A-DOA2 | WeADAPT Artefact
- **URI:** https://w3id.org/np/RAIVlsZYgQ13_Z_qrtyV3eoXINcl8sEQc5Aqm-qLoidil/F2A-CS5A-DOA2
- **Type:** Article
- **Variables:** Climate Change related variables

Solution path:

- FAIRification
- Transformation of data to knowledge

Builds upon User Stories: F2A-CS5B-US1 | Platform manager improve search capability

3.5.3. Description 5B - Climate Connectivity Hub

- **Name:** F2A CS5B
- **URI:** https://w3id.org/np/RAzRxKQLBXdgHew_IcNRsZv7RJ0fPDBjLZKXQZ9DZ_3e0/F2A-CS5B
- **Description:** Automated adaptation content harvesting and visualisation (Pan-European)
- **Contact Point:** <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0152-4565>
- **Lead Partner:** Stockholm Environment Institute
- **Research Domains:** Climate Change Adaptation, Disaster Risk Reduction, Climate Change Mitigation
- **Spatial Coverage:** global
- **Temporal Coverage:** 2026-2027
- **Goals:**

- Improve Connectivity Hub to support communities, planners, practitioners, students, researchers and policymakers in accessing and sharing climate-resilient adaptation information and strategies
- Break down silos and avoid redundancy, replication, and wasted resources while promoting collaboration, dialogue, and learning, by harnessing the wealth of existing knowledge across various portals, platforms, and publications, and providing guidance on how to connect this knowledge together.
- Integrate Connectivity Hub in EOSC. Ensure that climate adaptation knowledge is accessible within EOSC, increasing its usability for a broad range of stakeholders.
- **Challenges:**
 - Users cannot quickly and easily find information, which impedes communication, coordination and collaboration.
 - Knowledge is increasingly online, but fragmented, unstructured and siloed.
 - Difficulty to provide a harmonised, accessible and integrated vocabulary.

User Story 1 (CS5B)

URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAQMxCJbVnokzWXQAFHyfB2pzsBeEXWpbcvwT4FZfUc2U/F2A-CS5B-US1>

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	Platform manager	improve the search capability	users can better find results
generalized	Infrastructure manager	optimize	share knowledge

Table 28: User Story F2A-CS5-US2

Input Digital Object(s):

- **Name:** F2A-CS5B-DOA1 | Climate Connectivity Hub
- **URI:** <https://w3id.org/np/RAlu0-0AACr4H1epuaNNF-OggOjQYMVDgX3-ECX8R2aDs/F2A-CS5B-DOA1>
- Type:** Registry
- Variables:** Climate Change related variables

Input Digital Object(s):

- **Name:** F2A-CS5B-DOA2 | Climate Connectivity Taxonomy
- **URI:** https://w3id.org/np/RAOHFYrmhkxwxtXPbpFEUo8PeALF5EjMr27gYIRz086_M/F2A-CS5B-DOA2
- **Type:** Semantic artefact
- **Variables:** Climate Change related variables

Solution path:

- FAIRification

3.5.3. FAIR Implementation Profile

URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAVgqppDFnLwV3SgHcGS0cv2MOedMKbMINGvLmvuTttj>

Question	FSR Type	FAIR Supporting Resource (in grey: planned to be used)
F2	Metadata schema	WP-MS Wordpress Metadata Schema
F2	Metadata schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
SF2-ME	Metadata editor service	ROHub Research Object Hub
SF2-VS	Validation service for metadata	FAIROS
F3	Metadata-data linking schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	WeAdapt-Platform
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	Connectivity Hub
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	ROHub Research Object Hub
A1.1 MD	Communication protocol for metadata	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
SA1.1-WA PI	Web-API	RESTful API Representational State Transfer
A1.2 MD	Authentication & authorisation service for metadata	Open Data
I1 MD	Knowledge representation language for metadata	JSON-LD JavaScript Object Notation for Linking Data
I1 MD	Knowledge representation language for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
SI1-FRS	FAIR representation service	Automated I-ADOPT Service
I2 MD	Structured Vocabulary for metadata	Climate Change Adaptation Taxonomy
SI2-ME	Metadata editor service	Graphologi
I3 MD	Semantic model for metadata	FAIR-enabling resource: MOD Metadata for Ontology Description and publication Ver 2.0
I3 MD	Semantic model for metadata	I-ADOPT Framework
R1.2 MD	Provenance model for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
R1.3-FES	FAIR Enrichment Service	Automated I-ADOPT Service

Table 29: FAIR Implementation Profile of Case Study 5

3.5.4. Gap Analysis

The requirements for this case study focus on enhancing the Climate Connectivity Taxonomy. While this semantic artefact already exhibits several FAIR characteristics, its reusability and extensibility are currently limited due to insufficient human accessibility. FAIR2Adapt will support

the publication of the taxonomy in public semantic artefact catalogues and in a FAIR repository, thereby enabling users to request extensions tailored to their specific use cases. In addition, the organisation of the associated corpus will be improved to transform the taxonomy into a hierarchical thesaurus, further enhancing the reusability of concepts within the Climate Connectivity Hub and weADAPT platforms. The I-ADOPT ontology will be applied to variables used in the online resources hosted by these registries. The resulting enriched semantic representations will improve search functionality by enabling semantic, faceted search capabilities.

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3.6. Case Study 6 - FAIRification of a Climate Adaptation Strategy

3.6.1. Description

- **Name:** F2A-CS6 | FAIRification of a Climate Adaptation Strategy: Improving the accessibility and usability of adaptation information for policymakers
- **URI:** <https://w3id.org/np/RAsMzQctI9nFAgodP8VDWbxmuuKvAELkxDKQhclgOApZE/F2A-CS6>
- **Description:** Climate adaptation strategies are essential for guiding responses to climate-related risks at local and regional levels. These strategies often serve as reference documents for policymakers, practitioners, and other stakeholders involved in planning and implementing adaptation measures. This case study supports effective science-policy communication by improving accessibility, usability and clarity of climate adaptation strategies.
- **Contact Point:** <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0787-5108>
- **Lead Partner:** Adelphi Research
- **Research Domains:** Urban Planning, Environmental Science, Climate Risk, Climate Change Adaptation, Human Geography, Physical Geography
- **Spatial coverage:** Germany
- **Challenges:**
 - Coordination: Lack of central integration and coordination of processes and information, since municipal utilities, geoinformation services, and other data controllers often work independently. Different responsibilities and priorities impede cooperation, e.g. for data requests/data and information management.
 - Rights and Licenses: There are uncertainties regarding data (protection) framework: transfer, usage, rules, rights and licenses.
 - Access and Availability: District councils, citizens, and government agencies currently have only limited and user-unfriendly access to information and data; often, there is no district-specific information available. This can make it difficult to support adaptation measures in private and public spaces.
 - Communication: Fragmented communication channels; accessibility requirements (language, readability, disability); trust gaps; constrained communications capacity.
- **Goals:**
 - to improve the implementation of Bremen's climate adaptation strategy
 - to improve accessibility and awareness among all citizens
 - to prepare data and information in a target-group oriented manner that triggers concrete actions
 - to increase FAIR and data transparency law awareness

3.6.2. User Stories

User Story F2A-CS6-US1 | Landeszentrale Klimaanpassung Bremen/Referat 43 prepares data

URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAjqp1uxaTCnuMvn8lnRPIQvZX5h9aWHGDY04WZg7pXxl/F2A-CS6-US1>

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	Landeszentrale Klimaanpassung Bremen/Referat 43 climate adaptation coordinator of city and state of Bremen	prepare data and information to a local scale of the climate adaptation strategy	to provide actionable recommendations and measures for local decision makers (Ortsteilbeirat)
generalized	local government representative	downscale	provide recommendations

Table 30: User Story F2A-CS6-US1 | Landeszentrale Klimaanpassung Bremen/Referat 43 prepares data

Input Digital Object(s):

- Name:** F2A-CS6-DOA1 | Klimaanpassungsstrategie 2025
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAoJgdhvNvTDoYrkaV2gqZ5SLmGNRUB4Kd76QydFSGa5E/F2A-CS6-DOA1>
Type: Text-based data; Policy document
Variables: climate risks; adaptation and measures; heat; heavy precipitation;
- Name:** F2A-CS6-DOA2 | Starkregenkarte
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAbzsm55q6vqmbLGOTcekRtqud4gin73aHPH2vW6uZ8O8/F2A-CS6-DOA2>
Type: Raster Map
Variables: water levels for three different precipitation scenarios
- Name:** F2A-CS6-DOA3 | Stadtklimaanalyse
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RASVs9GA8-dSRkN-SJXBSXBt9zG0kGZiG5IO0ajblRU3Q/F2A-CS6-DOA3>
Type: Text-based data; policy document
Variables: air temperature at 2m above ground level; flow field at 2m above ground level; physiologically equivalent temperature at 1.1m above ground level;
- Name:** F2A-CS6-DOA4 | Hot Days
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAc-QwFDDaN3N9gprMe3jWJcH3LIyGi6nhkKQuOKzylw/F2A-CS6-DOA4>
Type: aggregated data; time-series data
Variables: number of days with temperatures above 30°C per year; average number of days with temperatures above 30°C per year from 1961-1990;
- Name:** F2A-CS6.DOA5 | Heavy Precipitation Days
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAxZ2kr6AcmUbXyne4jXc3nSmGhiarTGAui5A4XFEyoDg/F2A-CS6-DOA5>
Type: time-series data

Variables: average number of days with heavy (>10mm/h) precipitation per year in Bremen and Bremerhaven from 1961-1990;

Solution paths:

- FAIRification
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard
- Transformation of data to knowledge

User Story F2A-CS6-US2 | local decision maker interprets and uses relevant data

URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAS-ldjguP61He7-6VUa1PdEZrXjPaxjeWrJtVxAcB4Cg/F2A-CS6-US2>

	As a ... (role)	I want to... (action)	so that... (purpose)
specific	Local decision maker (Ortsbeirat)	downscale and visualize information from the climate adaptation strategy to a local scale	we can prepare measures and engage citizens
generalized	local decision maker	downscale	engage stakeholders

Table 31 User Story F2A-CS6-US2 | local decision maker interprets and uses relevant data

Input Digital Object(s):

- **Name:** F2A-CS6-DOA1 | Klimaanpassungsstrategie 2025
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAoJgdhvNvTD0YrkaV2gqZ5SLmGNRUB4Kd76QydFSGa5E/F2A-CS6-DOA1>
Type: Text-based data; Policy document
Variables: climate risks, adaptation and measures, heat, heavy precipitation
- **Name:** F2A-CS6-DOA2 | Starkregenkarte
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAbzsm55g6vqmbLGOTcekRtqud4qin73aHPH2vW6uZ8O8/F2A-CS6-DOA2>
Type: Raster Map
Variables: water levels for three different precipitation scenarios
- **Name:** F2A-CS6-DOA3 | Stadtklimaanalyse
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RASVs9GA8-dSRkN-SJXBSXBt9zG0kGZiG5IO0ajblRU3Q/F2A-CS6-DOA3>
Type: Text-based data; policy document
Variables: air temperature at 2m above ground level; flow field at 2m above ground level; physiologically equivalent temperature at 1.1m above ground level
- **Name:** F2A-CS6-DOA4 | Hot Days
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAc-QwFDDaN3N9gprMe3jWJcH3LiYGi6nhkKQuOKzylw/F2A-CS6-DOA4>
Type: aggregated data; time-series data
Variables: number of days with temperatures above 30°C per year; average number of days with temperatures above 30°C per year from 1961-1990;

- **Name:** F2A-CS6.DOA5 | Heavy Precipitation Days
URI: <https://w3id.org/np/RAxZ2kr6AcmUbXyne4jXc3nSmGhiarTGAui5A4XFEyoDg/F2A-CS6-DOA5>
Type: time-series data
Variables: average number of days with heavy (>10mm/h) precipitation per year in Bremen and Bremerhaven from 1961-1990;

Solution paths:

- FAIRification
- Implementation of user-interactive dashboard
- Transformation of data to knowledge

3.6.3. FAIR Implementation Profile

URI: https://w3id.org/np/RAGx_3E2Tx3pU0OAe0WnVSdlDNk9OiToCcHhHaVpwWB1s

Question	FSR Type	FAIR Supporting Resource (in grey: planned to be used)
F1 MD	Identifier service for metadata	DOI Digital Object Identifier
F2	Metadata schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
SF2-ME	Metadata editor service	ROHub Research Object Hub
SF2-VS	Validation service for metadata	FAIROS
F3	Metadata-data linking schema	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
F4 MD	Registry for metadata	ROHub Research Object Hub
A1.1 MD	Communication protocol for metadata	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
A1.2 MD	Authorization and authentication service for metadata	Open Data
I1 MD	Knowledge representation language for metadata	JSON-LD JavaScript Object Notation for Linking Data
I1 MD	Knowledge representation language for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
I1 D	Knowledge representation language for datasets	Portable Document Format (PDF)
S11-FRS	FAIR representation service	Automated I-ADOPT Service
I2 MD	Structured vocabulary for metadata	IPCC Glossary
I2 D	Structured vocabulary for data	IPCC Glossary
S12-ME	Metadata editor service	nanodash
I3 MD	Semantic model for metadata	I-ADOPT Framework
R1.1 MD	Data usage license for metadata	CC BY 4.0 Attribution 4.0 International
R1.2 MD	Provenance model for metadata	RO-Crate Research Object Crate
R1.3-FES	FAIR Enrichment Service	Automated I-ADOPT Service

Table 32: FAIR Implementation Profile of Case Study 6

3.6.4. Gap Analysis

Currently, data are accessible only as pdf with no metadata attached, published only on institutional websites. For FAIRification of pdf's, the use of ORKG could be considered. The fip declares the intended use of DOIs for metadata, and should do the same for datasets. The intended use of RO-crates as metadata schema, data-metadata linking schema, and provenance model, as well as metadata registry in ROHub and on Nanodash, are very promising for FAIRification. Datasets should additionally be added to registries. Regarding accessibility and licensing, uncertainties about data protection need to be addressed in order to select suitable FAIR solutions. Where possible, data will be openly accessible under a CC BY 4.0 license. When metadata records are provided, The I-ADOPT service is intended to be used when available to annotate the variables as machine-readable representations using the IPCC Glossary as semantic resource.

4. Next Steps

The requirement elicitation process described in this deliverable establishes the foundation for the FAIR2Adapt project's year 2 activities. This chapter outlines the key next steps that will build upon the user stories and FAIR Implementation Profiles documented for each case study, moving from requirements gathering to practical implementation. The FAIRification Framework (D3.1) will be used to develop FAIRification plans and execute them for each case study, transforming the identified requirements into concrete FAIR Digital Objects.

4.1. Interrelationship between the case studies

The six FAIR2Adapt case studies are not isolated endeavours but form an interconnected ecosystem with significant synergies and complementarities. As documented in D6.1, the case studies can be grouped according to their primary contributions to the adaptation knowledge value chain:

Scientific Data Production and Modelling (CS1–CS3):

- **CS1 (Arctic):** Conveys large amounts of scientific information about radionuclide distribution and environmental safety
- **CS2 (RiOMar):** Conveys large datasets to diverse stakeholders for coastal water quality assessments
- **CS3 (Hamburg):** Focuses on stakeholder engagement and capacity building for urban climate risk assessments

Knowledge Translation, Capacity Building and Decision Support (CS4–CS6):

- **CS4 (Portugal):** Translates grey literature into machine-readable information for the national adaptation hub
- **CS5 (weADAPT/CCH):** Creates a connected, interoperable ecosystem for adaptation knowledge and facilitates human-centred processes in climate adaptation
- **CS6 (Bremen):** Translates scientific data into policy and financial language for municipal stakeholders

Key cross-cutting synergies identified:

- **Shared pipelines:** CS2's pipeline for subsetting information based on end-user needs can be leveraged by CS1; CS3's pipeline to FAIRify GIS workflows can be directly reused by CS6 for the City of Bremen
- **Common vocabulary:** The weADAPT taxonomy developed in CS5 will be used across all case studies to ensure semantic interoperability
- **Literature extraction:** The literature review and extraction pipeline developed for CS4 and CS5 can benefit both national hub development and the global weADAPT community
- **Grey literature translation:** Both CS4 and CS6 face similar challenges in making municipal adaptation strategies machine-readable, enabling shared solutions

Year 2 activities will explicitly leverage these interrelationships through coordinated action plans that share tools, methods, and lessons learned across case studies.

4.2. FAIR Solution Demonstrators

A critical milestone for Year 2 is the presentation of four FAIR solution demonstrators at the General Assembly in March 2026. These demonstrators will showcase how the FAIRification framework connects to concrete case study needs and demonstrate the tangible value of FAIR for adaptation decision-making. Each demonstrator is linked to specific user stories documented in this deliverable:

FAIR Solution 1: Data Processing Pipeline for Coastal Water Quality (CS2 RiOMar)

Purpose: Enable regridding of simulation output to another grid (DGGs-Healpix), FAIRify it, and integrate in a STAC catalogue—overcoming the limited accessibility and usability of model data.

Related User Stories: F2A-CS2-US1, F2A-CS2-US2, F2A-CS2-US3

Services Involved: STAC catalogue integration, DGGs Healpix-geo regridding, visualisation of DGGs-regridded datasets, RO-Crate profiles, I-ADOPT for oceanographic variable descriptions, P4A visualisation platform, EGI DataHub for large-scale storage

FAIR Solution 2: FAIR GIS Workflow for Urban Climate Risk Assessment (CS3 Hamburg)

Purpose: FAIRify the software (GIS pipeline to generate risk assessment maps) to create a workflow that can easily be reused in CS6 for the City of Bremen and/or transfer cases—demonstrating cross-case replicability.

Related User Stories: F2A-CS3-US1, F2A-CS3-US2, F2A-CS3-US3

Services Involved: Galaxy workflow engine investigation, GitHub repository with Codemeta + SOMEF metadata extraction, WorkflowHub registration, Zenodo publication, RO-Crate packaging

FAIR Solution 3: Knowledge Production from Scientific Publications (CS3 Hamburg)

Purpose: Make scientific claims and workflows verifiable and reusable for other researchers who wish to reuse knowledge or build upon similar methods.

Related User Stories: F2A-CS3-US3

Services Involved: Metadata extraction service (topics, keywords, entities), scientific claims extraction and verification, I-ADOPT variable descriptions, ROHub publication, RO-Crate with enriched metadata

FAIR Solution 4: Literature Review and Extraction Pipeline (CS4 Portugal + CS5 weADAPT)

Purpose: Compare manual vs. LLM-based extraction and create machine-readable systematic reviews using the TIB Knowledge Loom—outcomes uploaded to weADAPT to benefit the global adaptation community.

Related User Stories: F2A-CS4-US1, F2A-CS4-US2, F2A-CS5-US1, F2A-CS5-US2

Services Involved: PRISMA framework with nanopublication templates, ExpertAI content extraction, automated vs. manual extraction comparison, RO-Crate packaging, Knowledge Loom integration

These demonstrators were selected based on feasibility (achievable outcomes within the project timeline), demonstration of FAIR value for adaptation practitioners, and replicability potential across case studies and future transfer cases.

4.3. Transfer Cases

Task 6.3 (starting M18) will leverage the strategic partnership with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC to develop transfer cases that demonstrate the scalability of the FAIR2Adapt FAIRification framework beyond the initial six case studies. Transfer cases represent additional climate adaptation contexts relevant to the EU Mission on Adaptation and EOSC.

Identified synergies with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC case studies:

CA4EOSC Case Study	Focus	FAIR2Adapt Synergy
Athens Urban Heat	Just-CURS digital twin; citizen engagement	CS3 Hamburg - urban heat methodologies
Portugal Coastal Wetland	OPENHIDRA flood forecasting	CS2 RiOMar, CS4 Portugal - coastal data
France Clay Shrink-Swell	Space2Earth geotechnical risk	CS6 Bremen - infrastructure risk

Table 33: Synergies with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC case studies

Key milestones for transfer case development:

- **MS6.4 (M21):** First meeting for future uptake via EU Mission
- **MS6.5 (M24):** Confirmation of 2 transfer cases with Mission Adaptation signatories
- **D6.3 (M36):** Report on uptake activities via EU Mission and EOSC

The user stories and FIPs developed for the initial case studies will serve as templates for rapid deployment in transfer cases, demonstrating the adaptability of the FAIR2Adapt approach to new domains and regions.

4.4. From User Stories to Use Cases

A key outcome of the requirement elicitation process is the ability to generalize specific user stories into broader use cases that can be applied across disciplines, systems, and regions. This generalization process is essential for creating reusable patterns and building a repository of FAIR solutions.

Generalization methodology:

Each user story in FAIR2Adapt follows the template: "As a [user], I want to [activity], so that [benefit]." The three components can be abstracted into controlled vocabulary terms:

Component	Specific (Text)	Generic (Controlled List)
As a...	user	role
I want to...	activity	action
So that...	benefit	purpose

Table 34: Abstraction of User Stories

Broader scope and outlook:

The generalization process will enable the creation of a repository (accessible via SPARQL queries) of use cases for specific digital object (DO) types and variables (aligned with I-ADOPT). This repository will include related roles, actions, and purposes to identify suitable FAIR Supporting Resources (FSRs) and guide users in achieving FAIR Solutions.

Processing steps for Year 2:

1. Specify FIPs where needed for Digital Objects
2. Complete FAIR assessments based on the FIPs documented in this deliverable
3. Derive FAIRification plans based on assessment results
4. Decide on required solution paths (FAIRification, data stewardship support, capacity building)
5. Specify and execute action plans for each user story
6. Enrich variables aligned with I-ADOPT framework
7. Generalize user stories using controlled vocabularies (role, action, purpose)
8. describe and link solutions as FDO RO-Crates in ROHub

The user requirements documented in this deliverable, combined with the Digital Object Analysis and FAIR Implementation Profiles created in the FIP Wizard, provide the foundation for executing these steps. The Helpdesk (T5.4) will support case study communities throughout this process, and the demonstrators presented at the General Assembly will validate the approach before broader rollout to transfer cases.

4.5. Summary and Timeline

Year 2 represents a critical transition from "understanding FAIR" to "using FAIR"—with communities as owners of solutions rather than respondents to technical questions. The key deliverables and milestones for the next steps include:

- **M15 (March 2026):** Alpha release of Knowledge Services (MS4.2); General Assembly with four FAIR solution demonstrators
- **M18 (June 2026):** 1st release of Customised CCA-related Services (D5.3); FAIRification services description (D3.2); •
- **M24 (December 2026):** Community Capacity Building Report (D5.1)

The user requirements, user stories, and FIPs documented in this deliverable establish the baseline from which all these activities will proceed. Success will be measured not by technical compliance but by whether the FAIR solutions developed actually support adaptation decision-making in the communities served by each case study.

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6. Annexes

List of figures

Fig.1: Case Studies versus User Stories.....	12
Fig. 2: Case Studies, User Stories and Digital Objects.....	13
Fig. 3 The FAIR Guiding Principles.....	13
Fig. 4 The core FIP questionnaire.....	14
Fig. 5 The FAIR Supporting Resource Types.....	15
Fig. 6: FAIR analysis of Digital Objects.....	17
Fig. 7: Processing phases in the requirement elicitation process.....	18
Fig. 8: Elements of FAIR implementation.....	22

List of tables

Table 1: Glossary.....	9
Table 2: Decomposition of a User Story.....	12
Table 3: Information elements of Case Studies.....	19
Table 4: Information elements of User Stories.....	20
Table 5: Information elements of Digital Object Analysis.....	21
Table 6: Information elements of FIP metadata.....	22
Table 7: User Story F2A-CS1-US1 Scientist integrates observations.....	25
Table 8: User Story F2A-CS1-US2 Scientist generates time-series data.....	26
Table 9: User Story F2A-CS1-US3 Scientist plots maps.....	27
Table 10: User Story F2A-CS1-US4 Scientist provides interpretation.....	28
Table 11: Basic FAIR Implementation Profile for Case Study 1.....	30
Table 12: User Story F2A-CS2-US1 Data manager optimizes workflow.....	32
Table 13: User Story F2A-CS2-US2 Policy maker select variables.....	32
Table 14: User Story Researcher configures scenario.....	33
Table 15: User Story Policy maker develops measures.....	34
Table 16: User Story Data analyst develops success indicators.....	34
Table 17: Basic FAIR Implementation Profile for Case Study 2.....	36
Table 18: User Story F2A-CS3-US1 Researcher shares tool.....	37
Table 19: User Story F2A-CS3-US2 Researcher integrates data.....	38
Table 20: User Story F2A-CS3-US3 Researcher makes paper machine-processable.....	39
Table 21: Basic FAIR Implementation Story for Case Study 3.....	41
Table 22: User Story F2A-CS4-US1 Researcher shares resources.....	43
Table 23: User Story F2A-CS4-US2 Private companies access policy.....	44
Table 24: User Story F2A-CS4-US3 NGO officer produces studies.....	44
Table 25: User Story F2A-CS4-US4 Policy owner finds information.....	45
Table 26: User Story F2A-CS4-US5 Municipal executives find relevant information.....	46

Table 25: Basic FAIR Implementation Profile for Case Study 4.....	49
Table 27: User Story F2A-CS5-US1.....	51
Table 28: User Story F2A-CS5-US2.....	52
Table 29: FAIR Implementation Profile of Case Study 5.....	53
Table 30: User Story F2A-CS6-US1 Landeszentrale Klimaanpassung Bremen/Referat 43.....	56
Table 31 User Story F2A-CS6-US2 local decision maker interprets and uses relevant data....	57
Table 32: FAIR Implementation Profile of Case Study 6.....	59
Table 33: Synergies with CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC case studies.....	62
Table 34: Abstraction of User Stories.....	63

F2A Draft